

STATISTICAL THEORY OF FRACTURE OF FIBRE COMPOSITES

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It is known (1) that during the fracture process of a composite material consisting of brittle fibres imbedded in a work-hardened matrix multiple breakage of fibres takes place. The breaking process influences severely the structure of the matrix. A model of the kinetics of the breakage of the fibres under homogeneous stress is considered based on the thermofluctuational conception of fracture (2) and on the following assumptions.

1. The probability of the fracture of a fibre segment of length x during the time Δt is $f(x)\Delta t + O(\Delta t)$, where $f(x) = \tau^{-1}(x)$ is inverse the mean life time of a fibre segment of length x . If we admit that the probability of of fracture at the distance z from any end of the fibre segment is $\phi(z)dz = \frac{\sigma z}{xx} \left(1 - \frac{z}{x}\right) dz$, then

$$\tau^{-1}(x) = Cx \quad (x > \ell_0), \quad \tau^{-1}(x) = 0 \quad (x < \ell_0), \quad C = C_1 \tau_0^{-1} e^{-\frac{\{U_0 - \gamma\sigma\}}{T}}$$

where σ denotes the applied stress, T the temperature in energetic units, $U_0 - \gamma\sigma$ the activation energy of fracture, τ_0^{-1} the frequency of atomic vibrations, ℓ_0 the critical length of the segment (1).

2. The occurrence and the point of the breakage do not depend on neighbouring segments.

The assumptions 1 and 2 allow us to consider the breakage of fibres as a branching process (3).

The distribution function of the non-dimensional lengths $x = y/L$ at the moment of non-dimensional time $t = t'/\tau(x)$ is calculated provided at the moment $t' = 0$ all fibres were of length L .

$$h(x) = \frac{12t(1-x)xe^{-t} [1-(1-x)^2]^{1+3t(1-x)^2/2} + [t(1-x)^2]^{2/3} + e^{-t}\delta(x-1)}{[t(1+t^{-1}(1-e^{-t})) + e^{-t}]}$$

$\delta(x)$ denotes Dirac's delta-function.

A similar approach was used in calculating the growth rate of a macroscopic crack in a fibrous composite. According to Kelly (4) we suppose that the crack grows either by pulling the fibre segments out of the matrix before the edge of the crack or by their breakage at the crack tip. The competition of these two growth mechanisms explain the experimentally observed lowering of the effective surface energy of a growing crack. (5)

References

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4. A. Kelly, Proc.Roy.Soc. A 319, 95, 1970.
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DISCUSSION/Session 4

COMMENT: K.N. Street, Corbeil-Essonnes, France

Due to a mix up on the part of the organizers, Dr. Alts' paper was not included in the rapporteurs' review even though it was submitted before the conference deadline. As a consequence, Dr. Alts was given five minutes to present his own paper. Sincere apologies were offered to Alts who was present in Boston.

COMMENT: J.H. Underwood, U.S. Army Benet Weapons Lab

Some of the comments by Dr. Rosen and Dr. Wright on Wednesday could be interpreted as indications that fracture mechanics seldom applies to composites. This is not our experience. In B-Al, graphite epoxy, and the glass-epoxy described here whenever co-linear, i.e. mode I, crack growth occurs then the fracture loads can be best described by fracture mechanics.

QUESTION: Y. Lindblom, Linkoping, Sweden

The deterioration occurs due to coalescence of the carbide. Have you tried to determine the connection between the change in surface area of the carbide and the deterioration of mechanical properties?

ANSWER: Messrs. David and Brody, University of Pittsburgh

The observed decrease in rod density with annealing time must result in a decrease in interfacial area which may be estimated from

the equation of Bayles et al. (Trans TMS-AIME, 239, 1969, 844-849). It is worth repeating that the structure along the growth direction remains stable during the observed coarsening. Any observed change in mechanical properties may be related to the decrease in the rod density and, also, to the distribution and morphology of the carbide phase. Although our paper did not report data on the mechanical properties of Nb-Nb₂C, high temperature mechanical properties are being studied. We expect to report preliminary results at the Conference on In-Situ Composites II in September 1975.

QUESTION: V.G. Lutsau, USSR

Using electron microscopy, have you seen any change in the mechanism of plastic deformation, e.g. slip to twinning, during impact tests as a result of the alloying with Ni? If so, what is the influence of such on crack initiation?

ANSWER: Messrs. A.R. Nicoll and P.R. Sahn, Heidelberg, Germany

We have done some electron microscopy on the basic eutectic material, i.e. without Ni-additions, and have seen numerous stacking faults in the matrix (Co-30 wt % Cr). We assume, however, that because the stacking fault energy increases with Ni-additions the number of stacking faults should decrease in the Ni-modified material. We believe that the reason for the higher impact strength must be sought by considering the ductilization of the matrix (see also text of paper), i.e. improved resistance to crack initiation as well as propagation.

QUESTION: M.J. Owen, Nottingham, England

Dr. Dharan, your strain criterion appears to be the same as one of the criteria suggested in the standard BS 4994. This is an inadequate criterion and may well be uneconomical because it is too stringent and particularly because it specifies a single value maximum strain. In fact, even the simplest fatigue cycle requires the values of two parameters and multiaxial conditions require more than two.

ANSWER: C.K.H. Dharan, Ford Motor Company, Dearborn, Michigan

The main aim of the paper was to contrast the fatigue failure mechanism in glass fiber and graphite fiber/polymer composites. The strain criterion was suggested as a simple explanation for the difference in fatigue behavior between the two materials. As specifically stated in the paper, it is to be applied only to the case of a unidirectionally reinforced composite in which the applied cyclic stress in uniaxially zero-tension or zero-compression parallel to the reinforcement. For other angles and for multiaxial loadings, all the strain components will have to be evaluated and

used in an appropriate yield criterion to predict failure.

With these qualifications, the criterion may be used as an indication of the likelihood of high-cycle fatigue failure, and was not proposed to be used as a design criterion. In many stiffness controlled applications, however, the criterion may not be unrealistic especially if environmental effects contribute to increased degradation rates once matrix and microcracking is initiated.

QUESTION: T. Hayashi, Chou University, Tokyo

Dr. Prabhakaran, could you show us a photo of the "necking" of your tension specimens or describe the essential features of the phenomenon observed?

ANSWER: R. Prabhakaran, Indian Institute of Technology

Professor Hayashi, I am providing two views of a "necked" 45° -orientation specimen (bidirectionally reinforced). As the photographs in my paper show, this necking phenomenon was observed for un-notched and notched specimens and also during static and fatigue loading, for a specific composite in the 45° orientation. The two views show the necking in the plane of the specimen and bulging in the side view. It was also observed that in the local region of final failure, the fiber bundles were aligned parallel to the axis of the specimen.

The following questions are addressed to G.C. Chang, U.S. Naval Academy, Annapolis, Maryland.

QUESTION: P.C. Chou, Philadelphia, Pennsylvania

What is the justification for using notched specimens for your impact tests? Is there any correlation between notched and unnotched specimens? Are the failure modes the same?

ANSWER:

Prior to full scale testing, I ran a series of pilot tests which revealed that notched specimens behaved differently from the unnotched. That is our justification for using both notched and unnotched specimens in our testing program. As you can see in the paper, failure modes associated with the two are somewhat different. There is a certain amount of direct correlation between the notched and the unnotched specimens, as shown in Table I of the paper (60% or so).

QUESTION: T. Hayashi, Chou University, Tokyo

Could you please explain the impact fracture modes for Type I and

Type II Charpy specimens?

ANSWER:

Impact fracture modes for Type I specimens are predominantly cleavage in nature. On the other hand, Type II modes are a combination of delamination and cleavage cracking, with the former being the dominant. Evidence is contained in reference 4 cited in the paper.

QUESTION: A. Rotem, Haifa

Have you examined the influence of notch direction relative to the laminae surface? Perhaps the fracture modes shown are a consequence of the direction of the blow and not the notch.

ANSWER:

The influence of notch direction relative to the laminae surface was investigated. In our Type I specimens, the notch is perpendicular to the laminae surface. The notch is parallel to the surface in our Type II specimens. Obviously they resulted in different failure modes. Incidentally, we did not vary the orientation of the notch in any Type II specimens, although we would have done it, resources permitting. Now let's compare results from Tests No. 1 (notched) and No. 8 (unnotched), the latter resembling Tests No. 2 as far as failure modes are concerned. Not only impact strength has changed but also the failure modes have changed. This tells us that fracture is influenced by both the existence of the notch and the direction of the blow.

The following questions are addressed to J.G. Morley, University of Nottingham.

QUESTION: K.N. Street, Corbeil, France

From a design standpoint, what effects will your relatively large diameter duplex fibres have on the size of composite structures where they may be utilized?

ANSWER:

There does not seem to be a problem in respect of the dimensions of the composite structure measured in a direction perpendicular to the fibre axis. For example, experimental systems consisting of a thin metal sheet, with a single layer of duplex elements attached directly to the surface of the sheet, have been constructed.

The core element stress transfer length has to be considered when dimensions are measured in the direction of fibre alignment. For existing laboratory systems having core elements of the order of

1 mm in diameter, the core element stress transfer length, at typical engineering stress and strain values, is of the order of a few centimetres. Reinforcing elements of the present size would therefore be applicable to engineering components having longitudinal dimensions greater than say 0.5 metres. These dimensions are, of course, related directly to the diameter of the element and depend on the frictional characteristics of the core/tube interface. It should be noted that in many engineering applications (e.g. a centrifugally loaded rotating component) the core and sheath can be directly bonded together at the point of attachment to the hub without loss of the failsafe characteristics of the core. The core stress transfer length at the free end of the component then only has to be considered.

QUESTION: W.B. Hillig, Schenectady, New York

The concept of a duplex fibre seems very attractive but it represents a real challenge to make such a fibre. What is the outlook for doing this on a scale needed for practical composites?

ANSWER:

There are various possible ways in which continuous two part reinforcing elements of the type described could be manufactured. For example, an initial grossly oversized tube (containing a semi continuous pre-formed convoluted core) could be drawn down to produce a tube of suitable dimensions. An adequate core/sheath interfacial frictional bond could be obtained by maintaining the core in tension during the drawing down process. Alternatively, the tube could be fabricated about the core from two layers of thin metal tape, each wound as a helix in the opposite sense. Bonding might be achieved by pre-coating one or both of the metal tapes with a suitable polymeric adhesive.

In the systems so far investigated the core elements have consisted of carbon or stainless steel wires. However, any elastic material could be used including for example a resin bonded carbon fibre bundle manufactured in a convoluted form by appropriate pultrusion techniques.

QUESTION: M.R. Piggot, Toronto

The ideas presented by Professor Morley have a fairly respectable lineage - Harris et al. have discussed stress transfer length and toughness and I have shown that under suitable conditions the fibres will always shrink away from the matrix at the crack face so a variable frictional force is produced. This produces a fracture work which tends to infinity. However, I do not believe that poor bonding between fibres and matrix is a practical approach. Better ways to maximize toughness include (i) maximize the fibre or bundle diameter (ii) minimize fibre modulus (iii) coat bundles

with a yielding layer (see Plendemann) (iv) use short fibres.

ANSWER:

The use of core/sheath duplex fibres gives us two types of reinforcing elements and two types of interface in the same composite structure. This avoids the problem of the conflict in interfacial requirements encountered when adequate toughness and longitudinal shear and transverse tensile properties are required of a composite material. See for example, J.G. Morley, Proc. Roy. Soc. London, A. 319, p. 1171-26(1970). The stress controlled decoupling/recoupling process occurring at the core tube interface is sufficiently powerful to prevent core fibre fracture whatever the tensile strain applied to the composite structure. As far as I am aware, these characteristics have not been reported in any other experimentsl fibre reinforced composite system.

Fibre non fracture has recently been observed to occur also under cyclic loading conditions. (McColl and Morley, Journal of Applied Physics, J. Phys. D. in press). It is certainly very well established that other things being equal, large fibres are helpful in improving composite toughness. It is usually undesirable, for engineering structural reasons, to minimize the fibre elastic modulus. As far as I am aware, coating fibre bundles with a yielding layer does not prevent tensile fracture of the fibre bundle occurring when the composite strain reaches a sufficiently high value. It has long been appreciated that toughness can be enhanced by the use of short fibres but this is at the expense of the strength and stiffness of the composite material, and the tensile failure process is localised because of the strain softening characteristics of fibre pull out. In the duplex reinforcing systems described, the core stress transfer lengths are relatively short at normal working stress levels, but increase rapidly with increasing overload values becoming infinitely large before the core element breaking stress is reached. The contribution of the core to the strength and stiffness of the composite is equivalent to that of a conventional fibre at engineering design stress levels, but complete structural integrity of the core reinforcing component is maintained and its contribution to the work of deformation of the composite is maximized.

The following questions were addressed to B.W. Rosen, Materials Sciences Corporation, Blue Bell, Pennsylvania.

QUESTION: T.T. Chiao, Livermore, California

Dr. Rosen, would you please comment on or defend Halpin's suggestion concerning the relation between strength and life distributions of a composite wherein he has to make two key assumptions (i) the

weakest one must fail first in life and (ii) the composite must gradually grow weak with time before catastrophic failure. We have done some work on fiber-glass composites which indicates that (ii) is questionable.

ANSWER:

The physical phenomenon underlying the work of Halpin and his colleagues is that a material fails because of some internal flaws or defects. Under repeated loads which are not of sufficient magnitude to cause static failure, there is a continual growth of these flaws or defects until, after repeated loadings, failure occurs. This failure is called fatigue. As I have pointed out in my lecture, different internal defects may lead to different failure mechanisms. The rate of growth of damage in these various failure modes can be different. Thus, there is no assurance that the flaws which are responsible for the weak members of the static population will indeed be those that are responsible for the weak members of the fatigue population. Thus, I do not accept the assumption that the weakest static member will be the one which of necessity will have the shortest lifetime. With regard to your second question, there are experimental data for composites in which residual strength increases first before it decreases. Thus, the change in composite strength with time may not be monotonic and I suppose it need not be gradual.

QUESTION: J.H. Underwood, U.S. Army Benet Weapons Lab

Dr. Rosen, you seem quite eager to severely restrict the application of fracture mechanics to composites. Would you agree that fracture mechanics can be applied to those composites which display co-linear growth?

ANSWER:

I am indeed eager to resist what appears to be a hurried and unsupported application of classical macroscopic fracture mechanics to composite materials. This does not mean that there are not cases in which fracture mechanics will apply. However, the fact that the initial damage propagates in a co-linear or self-similar fashion is not by itself an indication that fracture mechanics will apply, because there are cases in which a substantial degree of internal damage in the material in failure modes not associated with co-linear cracking can precede the final visible co-linear crack propagation. This would be the case for a slit notch in a ± 45 composite and probably also in a 0/90 composite tested in uniaxial tension.

QUESTION: I. Wolock, Washington, D.C.

Dr. Rosen, did you say in response to the question by J. Underwood

that it is necessary to be able to observe the crack to apply fracture mechanics to composites? Secondly, your observations regarding fracture mechanics appear to be directed toward a micromechanics approach. This is a severe and unnecessary limitation since a macromechanics approach is really adequate for fracture mechanics analysis.

ANSWER:

We have two separate problems that we must deal with. The first is an understanding of the influence of microscopic birth defects in the material upon its subsequent behavior under repeated loading. The second is a question of fracture resulting from a macro discontinuity such as a bilt hole. I believe the application of fracture mechanics to composites is questionable on both the micro and the macro scale as a general tool for fracture analysis. My primary concern here was on the micro scale because I was addressing the question of growth of birth defects leading to fatigue failure. I believe that it is true that initial growth and accumulation of micro defects involves a number of different failure mechanisms. Thus a micro-fracture analysis including multiple modes is necessary, whether it utilizes classical fracture mechanics concepts or otherwise.

When there is a macro defect, and a self-similar propagation from the initial defect, it may be possible to measure fracture mechanics parameters which can be applied to other macro defects in the same composite material. Further experimentation and analysis is required to determine whether even in this limited case such a fracture mechanics approach is valid, or desirable.

QUESTION: M.K. Smirnova, Leningrad

Dr. Rosen, is your approach to crack initiation and propagation the same for materials with comparatively soft and tough matrices? Could it not be more probable that for materials with soft matrices, the primary reason for crack initiation is the nonuniform tension (perhaps he means strength-KNS) of the fibres?

ANSWER:

Your point is well taken, in that non-uniformities in the orientation of the individual filaments in a composite may result in a non-uniform stress distribution when load is applied to the composite. Thus, accumulation of fiber failures will be governed both by this variable stress from filament to filament, as well as by the statistical variation in filament strength. In that event my approach would be to consider the multiple yarn as the basic element experiencing tensile failure within the composite.

QUESTION: J.D. Buckley, Hampton, Virginia

Dr. Rosen, given the uniqueness of composite structures, have specific mathematical models been developed for the various families of composites (e.g. metal matrix, plastic matrix)? (KNS-presumably the question relates to strength predictions.)

ANSWER:

Again, this is another valid concern which must be treated in the strength analysis of composites. It is certainly reasonable to expect that the relative tensile and shear characteristics of a metal matrix composite will differ from those of a polymeric matrix composite, and hence, the likelihood of occurrence of different composite systems. Mathematical models for treatment of these distinctions exist in a somewhat limited state at this time.

QUESTION: M.J. Owen, Nottingham

Dr. Rosen dismisses fracture mechanics approaches. We have investigated Paris type crack propagation laws and found them to be very promising for glass mat and fabric laminates. They proved to be very helpful in dealing with size effects, damage tolerance and extrapolation to long lives (see J. Phys. (D), London, 1974).

ANSWER:

I do not dismiss fracture mechanics approaches; I dismiss only the a priori assumption that all composites will behave as homogeneous metals for all fracture mode problems. I believe that when the nature of the reinforcement in the composite material approaches randomness, the representation of such a material as a homogeneous continuum, even for fracture problems, becomes more realistic. Indeed, I am aware of the work for glass fabric laminates which does show fracture characteristics which can be well represented by the parameters of fracture mechanics.

QUESTION: G. Horvay, Amherst, Massachusetts

Dr. Rosen, you have not mentioned frequency dependent effects in your talk. In your estimation, are these important in composite structures?

ANSWER:

Yes. The bulk of the effort which has gone into understanding the mechanics of composite materials has been associated with static or quasi-static problems. As we improve our understanding of these, the shortcomings in our capabilities in the dynamics area are likely to become more pronounced. For example, frequency dependent effects are quite likely to be of importance in problems such as

composite material damping, which will be important for flutter problems.

The foll wing questions were addressed to T. Hayashi, Chou University, Tokyo.

QUESTION: B.W. Rosen, Blue Bell, Pennsylvania

Professor Hayashi, what advice can you offer the designer when he has to treat multiple loading conditions in the case of, for example, a cylinder that must resist both bending and torsion?

ANSWER:

As the author noted in this presentation, a cylinder was subjected to only torsional loading.

For the case in which a cylinder is subjected to bending and torsion simultaneously, a similar optimization procedure would be utilized, if only an appropriate failure criterion for such loading conditions could be established. Those failure criteria have not yet been firmly established. But for a thick walled cylinder, a phenomenological law of failure, such as Tsai's theory could be roughly applicable. For a thin walled cylinder, whose fracture is caused by buckling, the buckling load for multiple loading cannot be predicted theoretically. But some "interaction formula" for buckling load may be proposed: $(M/M_C)^{n_1} + (T/T_C)^{n_2} = 1$, where M_C and T_C denote the values of the buckling moments for each individual loading, and the superfix, n_1 or n_2 would be determined empirically. $n_1=1$ and $n_2=2$ may be a possible choice for axi-symmetrically orthotropic composite cylinders. Such a formula may be approximately utilized for the design optimization.

QUESTION: K.N. Street, Corbeil, France

Professor Hayashi, we know of your strong interest in the very worthwhile area of earthquake resistant housing design and construction. Could you tell us what are the principal design criteria for such structures and some of the advantages which fibre composite materials possess over conventional materials? Do you consider impact, high stress fatigue and damping capacity in such structures?

ANSWER:

Earthquake-proof structures have been extensively studied in Japan. The author has pointed out on several occasions the inherent potential of composite materials and useful construction concepts for this purpose. But, as for the research on the structural materials side, there remains a lot to be done. Namely the light weight, ap-

appropriate damping, stiffness and non-brittleness, which are required can be largely achieved by using composite materials and the introduction of those concepts.

QUESTION: B. Riseborough, Guelph, Ontario

Professor Hayashi, the use of the principal laminate moduli E_1 and E_2 in the buckling formulae is perhaps appropriate in the particular case considered (filaments at $\pm \theta$). However, for a true optimization, should not the possibility of varying the angle of the individual layers (or pair of layers) be considered and would it not be necessary to retain the rigidities D_1 and D_2 in the buckling formulae in this case? (KNS-W. Rosen added a comment to this question following Professor Hayashi's reply.)

ANSWER:

The author agrees with you. For the general optimization of a composite cylinder, it is better to retain the rigidities, D_1 and D_2 , in the buckling formulae. This is because they have more clear physical meanings than E_1 and E_2 as average macroscopic moduli, just as you have mentioned; and in general, for a laminate the in-plane moduli and out-of-plane moduli will differ.

GENERAL COMMENT: M.K. Shorshorov, USSR

The present position in the development of a theory for composite materials behaviour may be characterized by certain successes in the application of linear mechanics, creep and fatigue theories to ascertain both the conditions of optimum reinforcement and their behaviour under test and service conditions. However the development of microscopic theories remains far behind. We have no strong theory of internal stresses, deformation strengthening and fracture of composites in spite of the large amount of experimental results and the application of new methods such as laser holography, Moiré method, transmission electron microscopy and acoustic emission.

In this field, we believe it is very important to examine the different stages of deformation strengthening and the initial stages of crack formation. My colleague Dr. V. Eremenko and myself are studying the conditions of dislocation pile-up in the matrix near an interfacial boundary, taking into account the mirror reflection forces, for two systems:

(i) graphite - aluminium ($G_f / G_m \sim 20$)

and (ii) tungsten - nickel ($G_f / G_m \sim 2$)

It has been found that the minimum shear stress which forms the

pile-up is several times greater in the former system.

I propose to organize the international reserach program for composite theory development and hope that the conference committee will help in doing so before the second conference.